

STRATEGIES IN TEACHING ENGLISH AS A SECOND LANGUAGE AND STUDENTS' LANGUAGE PROFICIENCY

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ABSTRACT

Strategies in Teaching English as a Second Language confirmed to hold a contribution towards students' language proficiency and academic performance. This study investigated the teaching strategies used by English teachers to enhance the academic performance of students, level of English language proficiency of the students and examined if there was a correlation between teaching strategies and English language proficiency. The researchers surveyed 168 grade 11 students from both STEM and GAS strand, employing probability random sampling method. The researchers used quantitative research design, utilizing a survey-checklist questionnaire that consisted of two parts: (1) teaching strategies; (2) English language proficiency and employed median and spearman correlation. The findings revealed that teachers used diverse teaching strategies with grand median score (Md= 4.00) "agree" from respondents including multimedia, storytelling, group work, and interactive learning tools were used to enhance students' academic performance. Students generally reported to be in high proficiency level of English language since grand median is (Md = 4.00) that fell into scale of "high" in receptive skills like listening and reading, while expressing moderate confidence in speaking and writing tasks. The correlation analysis showed a positive but weak significant relationship between variables ($\rho = 0.240$, $p=0.002$), indicating that teaching strategies have contributed positively to language proficiency, however, there were some other factors affecting the components of language proficiency of students.

Keywords: *Strategies in Teaching English, English as a Second Language, Language Proficiency*

INTRODUCTION

The ability to communicate effectively in English is essential for students since English is regarded as a universal and primary language in global and international contexts. It is considered the official medium of communication by many countries to efficiently connect and understand one another better. Proficiency in English is essential for academic success and learning achievement as well as professional areas. Teaching English as a Second Language is beneficial in helping students acquire the necessary skills. Therefore, Manalo (2022) noted that English language proficiency is recognized as a significant factor for success in the globalized world. Opportunities for getting global job positions and improving someone's quality of life are possible for those who possess strong English language.

Teaching strategies involve the methods and techniques employed by teachers to mitigate the language proficiency and sustain students' enthusiasm. Thus, it makes student engage better in learning. Hayati et al. (2021) highlighted that strategies such as collaborative learning, project-based activities, and interactive exercises help students remain attentive, motivated, and interested in the subject matter, ultimately enhancing their academic performance. These strategies allow students to develop essential skills while making the learning process enjoyable and meaningful. In addition, Hashim et al. (2018) mentioned that English language involves several skills that learners need to develop for effective communication. These skills include listening, speaking, reading, and writing. Listening helps with understanding spoken English, while speaking allows clear expression of thoughts. Reading is essential for comprehending texts, and writing enables communication in written form. Hence, mastering vocabulary and grammar is important. Good vocabulary helps convey messages accurately while grammar ensures clarity. Thus, according to a study conducted by Tigarajan et al. (2016), language learners apply various learning strategies in order to enhance their proficiency in a given language. The academic institutions as well as the teachers are partially responsible and the key on improving the English skills and proficiency of students. Scrutinizing students' own learning preferences in strategies teachers apply is important, it helps teachers choose strategies that suit them better, eventually turning those strategies into habits that enhance their overall language learning abilities.

This study aimed to identify and evaluate the teaching strategies used for English as a Second Language that contributed to improving the language proficiency and academic performance of Senior High School students at Mindanao State University-Sulu. Specifically, it sought to explore various instructional methods, techniques, and approaches that enhanced students' engagement and language proficiency. The significance of this research lay in its potential to improve teaching practices and contribute to students' success. The findings of this study were expected to guide teachers in creating effective lesson plans to the unique needs of English language learners. An enlightenment of these strategies may lead to enhanced language acquisition, improved communication skills, and increased student confidence. Additionally, the results may breakdown and undercover strategies utilized for the professional development of teachers to refine their approach.

This study sought to recognize strategies in teaching English to aid the language proficiency of the students, serving as their driving force and to master the English language and to empower them at the same time. This was to lit the dim of challenges towards academic achievement and future career opportunities in an increasingly globalized society. However, it made emphasis to effective instructional strategies and contributed to the betterment of English as a second language education.

Research Questions

This study aimed to identify the strategies in teaching English as a Second Language and the language proficiency of Senior High School students of Mindanao State University-Sulu. Specifically, this study sought to answer the following questions:

1. What strategies do English teachers use to enhance students' academic performance?
2. What is the level of English language proficiency of the students?
3. Is there a significant relationship between the English language proficiency of students and teaching strategies employed in their classes?

1.2 Conceptual Framework

The figure showed the conceptual paradigm of the study indicating the independent variable and dependent variable.

Figure 1 Conceptual Model of the Study

Figure 1 represented the conceptual framework for this study. Strategies in Teaching English as a Second Language was the independent variable, whereas the Learning Achievement served as the dependent variable. The arrow in the diagram indicated that the independent variable was expected to influence the dependent variable. In other words, the relationship of these two variables indicated that teaching English as a Second Language strategies affected the students' language proficiency.

Literature Review

Teaching Strategies

Effective teaching strategies were taking into consideration of both the subject being taught and the students learning it. The teachers should take note the students' skill level, and preferred learning styles, along with the goals of the lesson. A teacher should level down according to the students' capability and may apply hands-on activities on students with medium level and discussion-based for advanced level. Students absorbed the information efficiently with this approach (Paragae, 2023).

Innovative teaching strategies were new and effective methods used to teach English as a second language, especially to teenage students. Ashrafova (2024) discovered that innovative teaching methods designed specifically for teenage English as a second language learners. These strategies included digital tools and content that was relevant to their preferences and also, applying this method improved students' language skills and kept them motivated and connected to this tool which was the strategy.

It was aligned with the findings of Pujati and Tamela, (2019) that emphasized the need for teachers to use innovative teaching strategies that met the needs of all students in an inclusive classroom. The concept of inclusivity in education has become important, attracting significant focus from educators worldwide. It was said that the necessity for teaching practices was not only to recognize individual differences but also to promote equal opportunities for every learner to refine their academic performance. In addition, Teachers can generate an engaging class and promote participation with the strategy.

Furthermore, Innovative teaching strategies often encouraged students to work together collaboratively in order to enhance and help each other to understand concepts and this strategy can provide a positive impact to the learning achievement and the academic performance. Nevertheless, these strategies created a more dynamic and flexible classes that can cause better retention and comprehension of new concepts. (Parker & Welch, 2021)

In the study conducted by Aryal (2024), he noted that using methods that build students' confidence in speaking included task-based learning. It provided plenty of chances for students to practice language in real-life situations. Approaches like task-based learning and communicative language teaching were highlighted in his study because it prioritized practical communication rather than just memorizing information. Additionally, giving feedback and conducting assessments were essential for tracking progress and finding areas that need improvement thus it brought a better outcome towards the learning achievement of students.

Clear instructions referred to specific, straightforward directions that helped learners understand what was expected of them in a task or activity. Djalilova (2023) stated the importance of utilizing clear instruction as effective teaching style saying that it was the need for clear instruction on language learning techniques, like mnemonic

devices, and teaching students when and how to use them. Helping students developed metacognition.

Furthermore, interactive techniques were teaching methods that encouraged students to participate actively in their learning, rather than just passively listening. Alisoy (2024) pointed out that effective English as second language teaching strategies involved using interactive techniques and integrating technology, which greatly improved language learning results remarking that interactive methods, such as group discussions, role-playing, educational games, and "language circles," actively involved students and boosted their speaking, listening, and confidence in using English. In addition, using digital tools, like language apps, online quizzes, multimedia presentations, and interactive whiteboards, further enhanced learning by improving understanding and vocabulary.

Akin to the study of Ponnaiah and Abdul Aziz (2022), who highlighted the benefits of using technology in English as second language classrooms, noted that it helped increase student engagement, motivation, and self-confidence adding that technology integration to the use of digital tools and resources in teaching to enhance the learning experience. Technology tools and applications encouraged more interactive learning, which reduced boredom and encouraged students to participate more. Making use of technology like netbooks, projectors, and internet access has changed how teachers taught and how students learned for the better. It intrigued and motivated English as second language to learners as well as gave them new experiences.

Direct strategies included techniques that enhanced cognitive skills like summarizing, using imagery and mnemonics, and compensation methods to fill knowledge gaps. Indirect methods involved metacognitive skills, emotional management, and social strategies to encourage collaboration. Khansir et al. (2023) explored various teaching methods for English as a second language, the study also advocated integrating all language skills (reading, writing, speaking, listening) and analyzing errors to provide specific feedback. Students would not be anxious to make mistakes and to ask questions that makes learning more efficient for English as second language learners, it expanded the students' courage in learning.

There were many teaching strategies that should be taken into account when teaching English as Second Language to students. Gibson (2016) pointed out that vocabulary development was the primary strategy that educators used to help these students improved their language skills. Focusing on vocabulary was essential because it served as the foundation for effective communication. When students have a strong vocabulary, they found it easier to understand what they read and heard, as well as expressed their thoughts clearly. Furthermore, a well-developed vocabulary did not only enhanced comprehension but also built students' confidence in speaking and writing. Students were more likely to engage in conversations and participate in class activities because they would greatly be equipped with new words and phrases noting that vocabulary development was crucial for helping English as Second Language students or learners to navigate their language-learning journey successfully.

Extracurricular activities were organized activities that students participated outside of their regular academic curriculum. They may include sports, clubs, and other non-academic pursuits that foster social, emotional, and cognitive development. Providing students with opportunities to practice their language skills outside the classroom was essential for language proficiency. Yol and Yoon (2020) affirmed that participating in extracurricular activities such as debates, public speaking contests, or drama clubs can be very advantageous in the academic field. These activities allowed students to apply their English skills in any field which ameliorate the development of students. Engaging in sort of activities does improve their fluency as well as cultivate essential skills like critical thinking, creativity, and effective communication, which were also important for successful language application in various circumstances. Furthermore, taking parts in debates develops students' skills to construct arguments and articulate their thoughts clearly, whereas drama clubs and role plays encouraged them to immerse into storytelling and character portrayal that reform their understanding of the language.

Nurhasanah et al. (2019) noted that modeling and interaction teaching strategies were efficient since students emulate the certain skills teachers demonstrate to their students which motivate and inspire them to mirror the behaviour of their teachers. Like when teachers demonstrate effective language use, which when the teachers engage in conversations that showcased proper pronunciation, vocabulary usage, and grammatical structures, it provides as a guidelines and framework for students to follow.

English Language Proficiency

Pandiangan and Gaol (2021) claimed that language proficiency was the ability to use a language effectively and accurately in different situations which included skills in listening, speaking, reading, and writing. Listening was defined as the understanding of spoken words, while speaking involved clear and fluent verbal communication. Reading was about understanding and analyzing written texts, and writing focused on using correct grammar, vocabulary, and organization. Language proficiency was often categorized into levels like beginner, intermediate, and advanced. Regular practice, frequent exposure to the language, and high-quality teaching that covered all four skills were the factors that influenced proficiency Assessments, whether formal tests or informal evaluations, helped identify strengths and areas that needed improvement. Language proficiency was important for academic success, effective communication, and cognitive growth, allowing individuals to access information, express their thoughts, and connect with different communities. In their study, effective teaching methods were marked as important for developing proficiency in senior high school.

Metacognitive Strategies were some of the most commonly used and effective methods for English as second language learners. They helped students plan, keep track of, and assessed their learning. These strategies were linked to better language skills and were favored by successful language learners. For example, students might set specific goals for their language study, like learning ten new words each week (planning). As they study, they can check if they understand the material (monitoring) and reflect on what

worked well or what did not work after a test (evaluating). Strategies like metacognitive method helped track progress and awareness that helped them become more proficient in the language (Irwand et al 2022).

Moreover, according to Duan (2022), language proficiency in senior high school referred to the ability to use language effectively and accurately across various contexts, encompassing components such as cohesion and coherence, which involved logical organization and smooth connections between ideas using appropriate linking words; lexical resources, requiring a strong vocabulary and precised word choice; and grammatical accuracy, including correct use of tenses, structures, and punctuation. Proficient writing also entailed employing effective writing strategies like planning, drafting, revising, and editing, while cognitive and affective skills, such as critical thinking, motivation, and self-confidence, played crucial roles in engaging with writing tasks. Improving proficiency demanded practice, feedback, and exposure to diverse styles, with educators fostering this growth through targeted instruction and authentic writing opportunities.

Collaborative and Multimodal were also fundamental strategies in improving language proficiency by boosting student engagement and motivation. They helped create lively learning environments that supported language growth (Salamanti et al., 2023). In cases at classroom, utilizing collaborative strategies, students might work together on a project, sharing ideas and practicing their language skills. Multimodal strategies may involve using videos, music, and hands-on activities to teach new concepts. The impact of these strategies was significant because when students were actively involved and using different methods to learn, they were more likely to enjoy the process and develop their language skills more effectively.

Kenol and Hashim (2022) looked on language learning strategies used by English as Second Language students to improve their English proficiency. The review found out that factors like socio-economic status, politics, education, and culture greatly affected the strategies learners choose. It highlighted that while students often preferred certain strategies, more research was needed on how they used multiple strategies at the same time to fully understand how effective they were. For instance, a student from a strong educational background might use advanced techniques like metacognitive strategies, while another student from a different background might rely on simpler methods like memorization. The impact of understanding these factors was significant for improving language proficiency. Educators can improve their teaching methods to better support all students. These factors can help achieve more effective language learning outcome and become more proficient in English and better equipped the learners to communicate in various situations.

Chen (2024) noted that the application of reading strategies in language acquisition included pre-, during- and post-reading strategies. These methods which have been included are pre-reading strategies such as recitations, cooperative reading, advanced organizers, and question-generation approaches contributed to language proficiency of srudents. Therefore, during-reading strategies, like skimming or selective

and intensive reading improved comprehension whereas post-reading strategies like mutual and self-reading and writing and reading logs reinforced understanding. Consciously, those who were successful language learners utilized such strategies as well as the less successful ones unconsciously. After a pre- and post test with all students, with the students in the strategy training condition outperforming the readership instruction condition, it indicated that explicit strategy training of the five-step training, consisting of strategy explanation, demonstration, review, independent practice, and application to new tasks, enhanced students' understanding of the texts and their interest in them. Incorporation of such training into the language learning courses ultimately enhanced the overall outcome by ensuring that learners read effectively and hence improved the language proficiency.

Proficiency based on Teaching Strategies

Villegas (2024) mentioned that teaching techniques should be selected with the understanding of the student's proficiency level. Continuing changes in academic performance across students meant that assessment, monitoring and feedback procedures were valuable to support instruction and differentiate student intervention. Formative and diagnostic assessment let the educators comprehend what the students knew and what they lacked so as to modify the kind of teaching that was done in order to suit the students' needs. In order to attend the learning needs of many students, teachers may have to employ methods of differentiation in instruction. For the struggling students, intervention processes, accommodation, and methods of differentiation were effective strategies. The on-going assessment and progress monitoring helped educators in making of instructional decisions and prescription of necessary variations. It was making emphasis that the assessment information was almost indispensable to inform teaching approaches that addressed the variety in student learning characteristics and achievement, to enhance learner progress.

According to Lubis (2024), Active Learning and Technology Utilization Strategies that used active learning, problem-solving, and technology can significantly boost English language skills. These strategies meant that teachers needed to be good at teaching and also familiar with technology for on-going assessment. Thus, a teacher might use interactive games or online quizzes that required students to actively participate. These were not only made learning more engaging but also helped students practiced their language skills in real-time. These strategies on language proficiency were profound because when students were actively involved in their learning and using technology, they were more likely to retain information and become more confident in their language abilities. This active participation led to improved communication skills and a better understanding of the overall language.

Vyn et al. (2019) found out that using the target language in class improved language skills, especially for beginners. However, teaching grammar directly has mixed effects since it might make learning not easier than it should be at first but eventually, it is a benefit for some students who's learning advance English. Beginners got the chance to hear and practice the language when teachers conducted an entire English lesson

which boosts their confidence and comprehension. On the other hand, if the teacher focused too much on grammar immediately, students might be confused and slow their progress. Using the target language was significant for language proficiency since it was said that when students were immersed in the language, they became more familiar with its sounds and structures and it leads to better speaking and listening skills. As they level up, a balance of grammar instruction can help refine their skills further.

According to Faez et al. (2017), there was a moderate connection between how well teachers knew a language and their confidence in teaching it. The amount of knowledge in language alone only accounted for a small part of their confidence, indicating that other factors also matter. In addition, a teacher might be very skilled in English but still feel unsure about teaching if they lack experience or support. Meanwhile, a teacher with less language skill might be very confident if they have strong teaching methods and classroom management skills, so this relationship on language proficiency was important. When teachers were confident, they were more likely to create engaging and integrated classes that encourage students to participate and practice their language skills. Therefore, it was essential to support teachers not only in improving their language skills but also in building their confidence and teaching abilities. It states that this combination can make better outcomes for students who were learning the language.

Rodriguez (2023) found that students who effectively used cognitive, metacognitive, social, and affective strategies showed higher grammatical competence and he highlighted that teaching students how to apply these strategies can significantly enhance their language proficiency. Metacognitive strategies, like planning and monitoring learning, were especially linked to better performance.

Synthesis

Teaching strategies for English as a second language were essential to develop the language proficiency of students. Different strategies were employed that is focused on making lessons interesting and relevant to the life of students. Hence, teachers can generate a classroom where students be engrossed and comfortable to participate in learning the language. It is indeed fundamental since actively involved students learned better and gained confidence. Teaching strategies went beyond just engagement as they were key in terms of developing language skills. Incorporating technology, giving clear instructions, and using hands-on activities makes students practice the language more often as well as integrating cognitive and social strategies. Furthermore, working together in groups can also enhance their language abilities and the teacher's skill and confidence impacts how well students learned. Hence, teaching strategies built a positive effect on the language proficiency of students with wise and appropriate utilization.

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

This study employed descriptive-correlational research design to investigate Strategies in Teaching English as a Second Language and students' language proficiency. This design involved the use of surveys to collect data and analyze findings. The descriptive-correlational method was a theory-based approach that explained the primary research topic by examining data and identifying relationships between variables. It focused on answering what, when, where, and how a phenomenon occurred but does not address why it happen. This type of research enabled an accurate and systematic description of a specific population, situation, or phenomenon (Williams, 2007).

Research Site

The study was conducted at Mindanao State University-Sulu, specifically in the Senior High School Department main building, which was located near the campus gymnasium at Capitol Site, Patikul, Sulu, where the data were gathered.

Respondents

The researchers randomly selected GAS and STEM students from Grade 11 level of MSU-Sulu Senior High School as the respondents for their study. The respondents were individuals from each strand, regardless of gender, within the Senior High School Department, and their selection was determined using the Survey Monkey Sample Size Calculator. As a result, the study consisted of 168 students, divided into groups of 28 for each section. The researchers used one of the probability sampling methods which was the stratified random sampling, to identify and select respondents, ensuring that everyone had a chance of being selected.

Research Instrument

The primary tool for data collection in this study was a Likert-scale survey questionnaire. This instrument was composed of structured statements intended to collect data on participants' experiences and perceptions regarding Strategies in Teaching English as a Second Language and students' language proficiency. Participants responded using a five-point Likert scale with the options: Strongly Agree, Agree, Neutral, Disagree, and Strongly Disagree. The questionnaire was divided into two parts: the first part consisted of close-ended questions focused on assessing the teaching strategies used by teachers, while the second part evaluated students' levels of English language proficiency. A total of 23 items were initially adopted from the study of Meenambal and Meenakshi (2022). However, based on the evaluation of three experts using the Content Validity Index (CVI), 14 items were included for the first part and only 3 items for the second part as the rest were omitted due to low validity ratings. The reliability of the instrument was confirmed through Cronbach's alpha with the first part showing a high

reliability score of 0.862 whereas the second part demonstrating reliability with a score of 0.762.

Research Ethics Protocol

The researchers were committed to upholding the highest ethical standards throughout the conduct of this study. They prioritized the privacy, confidentiality, rights, and overall well-being of all participants. The study was conducted in a manner that respected the dignity, autonomy, and welfare of each respondent. This ethical approach was intended not only to protect the participants but also to enhance the credibility, validity, and reliability of the research findings. Informed consent was obtained from all participants, and they were assured of their right to withdraw at any stage without any consequences.

Data Collection

The initial step undertaken by the researchers was the validation of the survey questionnaire through consultation with the designated research teacher. Following this validation process, the researchers sought a formal approval from Dr. Norman A. Abdurahman, the Director of Mindanao State University - Sulu Senior High School. Upon receiving approval, the researchers distributed the letter of consent to the advisers of the selected participants, granting permission to administer the survey to the target student sample. Once the data collection was completed, the researchers systematically organized and analyzed the responses using tabular presentations and appropriate statistical techniques. This comprehensive analysis has served as the basis for drawing the study's conclusions.

Statistical Techniques

The median was used to identify the most commonly employed teaching strategies by English teachers and evaluated the level of English language proficiency among students as well. Additionally, Spearman's rank-order correlation was utilized to determine the relationship between teaching strategies and students' English language proficiency since the data were not normal. These statistical methods were intended to provide an understanding of how various instructional strategies influenced English language learning outcomes.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Table 1

Strategies in Teaching English to Enhance Academic Performance

Statement	Md	Descriptive
1. My teachers are providing opportunities for learners to speak English in the classroom.	4.00	Agree

2. My teachers follow any special techniques to teach English.	4.00	Agree
3. My teachers are using course books to teach English.	4.00	Agree
4. My teachers are using different stories/examples related to the content of the textbook to make us understand the concept.	4.00	Agree
5. My teachers are using different videos/ audio clips related to the content of the textbook to make us understand the concept	4.00	Agree
6. My teachers are using different activities/materials related to the content of the textbook to make us understand the concept.	4.00	Agree
7. My teachers are using supplementary books related to the content of the textbook to make us understand the concept.	4.00	Agree
8. My teachers follow other materials like pictures or things to teach English in the classroom.	4.00	Agree
9. My teachers use roleplay activities to enhance my communication skills in English.	4.00	Agree
10. My teachers incorporate pair work to help improve my speaking and comprehension skills in English.	4.00	Agree
11. My teachers encourage group work to support my learning and academic performance in English.	4.00	Agree
12. My teachers use storytelling as a strategy to help me understand and use English more effectively.	4.00	Agree
13. My teachers include educational games to make learning English more engaging.	4.00	Agree
14. My teachers integrate technology in English language learning to enhance my academic performance.	4.00	Agree
Grand median	4.00	High

Note: 5.00-4.21= Strongly agree, 4.20-3.41 = Agree, 3.40-2.61 =Neutral, 2.60-1.81 = Disagree, 1.80-1.00=Strongly Disagree

Median was utilized to determine the strategies in teaching English to enhance academic performance. The median score for all items and its grand total in the table 1, which was (Md = 4.00), indicated unvaried response for all strategies which was 4 (Agree), that English teachers implemented multiple strategies to enhance students' academic performance showing strong consistency of agreement regarding the teachers applied strategies that included using course books and supplementary materials, videos, games, storytelling, stories, technology integration, pair work and group work, special techniques and classroom opportunities to speak English. The findings were similar to the previous study of Garganera, et al. 2024, they examined the strategies employed by English teachers to enhance the academic performance of graduate students in the Bicol Region, Philippines. The study found that teachers used a wide range of strategies to

improve students' language proficiency that contributed positively towards the academic performance of students.

Table 2
English Language Proficiency Level of Students

Statement	Md	Descriptive
1. I can speak well in English inside the classroom.	3.00	Moderate
2. I never speak in English to anyone in an informal situation.	3.00	Moderate
3. I can follow and understand instructions on forms and applications.	4.00	High
4. I have the capacity to speak English outside the classroom.	4.00	High
5. I can write grammatically correct sentences in English without difficulty.	3.00	Moderate
6. I can understand and respond appropriately to questions asked in English.	4.00	High
7. I can understand spoken English in conversations, lectures, or discussions without needing translation.	4.00	High
Grand median	4.00	High

Note: 5.00- 4.21= Very High , 4.20-3.41 = High, 3.40-2.61 =Moderate, 2.60-1.81 = Low, 1.80-1.00=Very Low.

Table 2 illustrated the level of students' English language proficiency. The grand median (Md = 4.00) interpreted as "High" indicated that students demonstrated a strong level of language proficiency overall. Four of the seven statements received a median score of (Md = 4.00), interpreted as "High". This included students' ability to follow and understand instructions, speak English outside the classroom, respond appropriately to questions, and comprehend spoken English in various contexts. Meanwhile, three items received a median of (Md = 3.00) "Moderate", implying uncertainty or lack of confidence in several skills such as speaking fluently inside the classroom, using English in informal conversations, and writing grammatically correct sentences. Nevertheless, the high grand median showed a generally competent level of English among the students. It was aligned with the study by Soliman and Gorospe (2024), they found that students demonstrated high proficiency in reading comprehension, there were moderately speaking in informal settings and grammatical accuracy.

Table 3
Relationship between English Language Proficiency and Teaching Strategies

Variables	n	1	2
Teaching Strategies	168	-	
English Language Proficiency	168	.240**	-

** Correlation was significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

A Spearman's rank-order correlation was conducted to determine the relationship between teaching strategies and English language proficiency among a sample of 168 participants.

The analysis indicated a weak positive correlation with coefficient between teaching strategies and English language proficiency with $\rho = 0.240$ and a p-value of 0.002 between the two variables, implying that the correlation was significant. These results indicated that an increase in teaching strategies was weakly associated with an increase in English language proficiency. However, other factors may influence this relationship since the correlation was weak.

In accordance with the study by Santos et al. (2022), which examined the relationship between teaching strategies and English language proficiency among students in the Philippines. They found a weak positive correlation between the teaching strategies implemented by teachers and the students' English language proficiency. Although the effect of teaching strategies on language proficiency was moderate, it signified other factors, such as individual learner characteristics and external influences for their proficiency.

Conclusions

The study has been undertaken and the findings showed that teachers implemented various teaching strategies to enhance students' academic performance to enhance students' academic performance. These methods were generally integrated and the students agreed that the strategies have contributed to their learning achievement. Subsequently, students demonstrated high level of competence in terms of English language proficiency but there were still some areas that needed assistance. They showed strength in understanding instructions, responding to questions, and engaging in conversations, though some expressed neutral confidence in informal speaking and writing with correct grammar. However, it resulted that there was a significant relationship between teaching strategies and English language proficiency but has a weak positive correlation. This indicated that teaching strategies did contribute to improve language proficiency, although other factors may also influence student performance. These findings found out that strategies in teaching English as a second language positively affected the students' language proficiency, although other external and personal factors also influenced the proficiency in English.

Recommendations

Research Agenda

1. **The school administrators** may support teachers by providing training on effective strategies for teaching English such as conducting workshops on using different methods like group activities, storytelling, and technology in the classroom. Administrators should also make sure that teachers have access to enough learning

materials such as books, videos, and digital tools to help teachers and students in learning English.

2. **The teachers** may still need to focus more on helping students improve their speaking and writing skills. In addition, teachers may include more activities that give students the chance to practice and exercise speaking, such as role plays and open discussions. In writing, teachers may urge students to write regularly through journals, essays, and short stories, meanwhile it also help them improve their grammar and sentence structure at the same time. Thus, teachers may evaluate students' skills regularly to assess their needs and adjust their teaching methods.
3. **The parents** may help their children improve in English by inducing them to use the language at home. This can be done by watching English shows together, reading simple English books, or having short conversations in English. Subsequently, parents should also praise their child's efforts, help them practice regularly, and consult with the teachers to stay updated on their child's progress.
4. **The students** may need to work on speaking more confidently and writing correctly. Taking part in class discussions, speak English even outside the classroom, and practice writing more often is highly recommended. And they may also use online resources or ask for help from teachers to improve in areas they are struggling with.
5. **The future researchers** may study other possible factors that affect students' English proficiency, such as their motivation, home environment, or access to resources. Further, future studies may also integrate interviews or observations to understand better how teaching strategies are used in real classrooms. Hence, reinforce to create a clear view of what works best for improving students' English skills.

Research Problem

1. External Factors Affecting the Relationship between Teaching Strategies and Students' English Proficiency
2. Teaching Strategy Methods towards the English Language Proficiency of Students
3. The Influence of Learner Motivation on the Effectiveness of English Teaching Strategies
4. The Impact of Student Engagement on the Effectiveness of English Teaching Strategies in Enhancing Academic Performance
5. The Effective Teaching Strategies to Enhance Students' Speaking Fluency in English

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The authors state that they complied with obtaining informed consent, the respondents' freedom to withdraw from the study at any time was respected, anonymity of the respondents was upheld, the respondents' well-being was protected, no conflict of interest exists in doing the study, plagiarism was stringently avoided, there was no partiality in the interpretation of the findings and that the results were used only for research.

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